

Interview ABSA 39-45 - Benoît Paquet
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution

ABSA 39-45 (Association Bretonne du Souvenir Aérien 39-45) is an association similar to Aerocherche, but focused on Pays de la Loire and Bretagne, in France.

Association born in 2004, in relation to an excavation of a Messerschmitt 109 aircraft. About 30 members today.

Since April 2021: association has been recognized of public interest. This new status allows better access to funding. It may facilitate the implementation of conservation measures (preventive or interventive) that can be costly.

The goal of the association is to document and tell the history of the fallen airmen in those regions.

They are mainly focused on wrecks on land, not so much underwater wrecks.

One of their main activities is to collect oral testimonials from veterans or people who were alive during the conflict, along with archival research in collaboration with different countries.

The association's members feel they have a duty of remembrance and get great satisfaction from helping families of fallen soldiers.

The association has carried out excavations from 2004 to 2010, no more since because the procedures for authorization have become more complex (authorization from the Prefecture, requires to involve miners).

Benoît Paquet (BP) is president of the association since 2019. He hears strong demands from the members to start archaeological excavations again, there 1 or 2 places in Brittany where there are still pieces of aviation identified by the association.

He expects Procraft to bring more clarity concerning the necessary procedures today.

The main concerns of the association are issues with conservation and especially with ownership of their artefacts.

Collection includes :

- no complete aircraft
- 2-3 engines (deformed),
- propeller blades, hubs
- various elements of "hard metal" which resisted to the fires during crash of aircrafts
- a few neutralized weapons (machine guns)

Most of their artefacts in the collection are large and heavy pieces with immediate visual impact, few small artefacts/parts who would need more detailed explanations.

These artefacts come mainly from former excavations, also some donations. In some situations they can help private persons who have kept objects at home.

The association also has about 100 models of fallen planes (scale 1/48), made in collaboration with a model club. The association would like to create dioramas with these models to recreate events and illustrate these scenes with real pieces from the aircrafts.

The association organizes regular and localized exhibitions/presentations, in response to requests from local municipalities who wish to commemorate events from WWII. They present all artefacts static, and take care of transport and all needed disassembly-reassembly operations. Usually pieces are presented directly in the trailer used for transportation.

The association is very worried of losing control over the pieces they have found (confiscated or given to another museum away from the local area). They feel they have committed funds to all their operations and would feel dispossessed, both financially and symbolically. They also feel that if they lose the artefacts they would be amputated of an important part of their identity and reason for existing.

The association is strongly attached to the local and regional aspect, and they would like to get recognition and paternity for having recovered the artefacts.

Example of a wing from a Spitfire aircraft in their collection : municipality of Binic wishes to retrieve it from them and put it on display in a memorial for the pilot.

Wish for a museum in Brittany that brings together all the local associations.

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

ABSA initiates the search and excavation.

They take care of the various procedures for authorizations : ask the owning country, conclude an agreement of the owner of the land, get the agreement and identification number from the DRAC (or DRASSM if underwater).

The association supports the full costs and efforts for organizing the excavations.

Procraft has raised new awareness for conservation needs after excavations.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

Preservation of the material itself is important, BP wish that the piece can be transmitted to future generations for itself and not only for the information it carries.

This concept was not always there for the association, vision has changed over time, in particular through discussions with Arc Antique.

They have never really questioned themselves about the treatment of whole planes, because there is little chance of finding any on land.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration?

Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

All members of the association are passionate about aviation and the history of their region, but they are not professionals in aeronautical field, conservation, or history. They are storekeepers, construction workers, commercial staff, nurses. Some have acquired skills within the association, e.g. on research in historical archives.

For the future museum, there is not yet a specific training project of the volunteers. The association relies heavily on the advice from partners, e.g. Arc Antique. Perhaps use of contractors if necessary and possibility for funding. Volunteers would be open to more training to better know the best practices.

The association would like to expand and increase numbers of members. They would also like to diversify the volunteers' backgrounds, as it would facilitate sharing skills and passion.

The association does not want to do restoration, they are not interested in bringing the artefacts to their original condition. They are precisely interested in the perception of damage and deformations, as they are better support to tell the story about the event. They wish to keep the artefacts as they are as much as possible .

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

The collection is currently stored in a storage room belonging to the municipality in Chateaubriant, a former fire station no longer used. The storage room was clean and dry, but without climate or pollutants control.

They have no exhibition space at the moment.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

No observation of visual changes in the condition of the artefacts.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

Pieces have been grouped in one place, whereas before pieces were dispatched to the different members.

Contact with Arc Antique for treatments

Before: Cleaning with water under pressure, dusting with dry cloth before an exhibition.

For future excavations: waiting to see what Procraft can offer

What has changed is the association's intention to stand out in front of specialists, which means being open to initiatives like Procraft, open to communicating with others in the field. BP intentionally wishes to be more in the light.

Wish to do things by the rules, as it is also a means of protecting the ownership of finds.

The association will have another image after the creation of the future museum, they will be perceived in a more positive way by DRAC, as there will be no possibility for selling the objects from the finds.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

No particular focus on issues for Al alloys, haven't noticed this issue more than others.
But BP says the association does not have the adequate skills to diagnose these problems

Usual treatments carried out : water cleaning and drying

No memory of particular corrosion problems with Al since BP arrived, no memory of having heard about treatments on Al alloys carried by others before his time.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

This is their raison d'être !

All pilot nationalities are taken into account in their research (Czechs, Germans, USA, Canada, Italy), they promote a pedagogical approach about the opponents of the conflict.